

RESPONSE PAPER

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FIRST NAME: MARY

PROGRAM CODE: PHGH

COURSE CODE: ACA-401D

PERIOD NUMBER: 1

INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did *not* use Zotero to insert referencesThe author did use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2007 on Windows 10)

Plagiarism – 3%

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Essay Writing Basics (EUCLID 2019, 1-4)
2. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2019, 5-13)
3. Rules of thumb for writing papers (EUCLID 2019, 14-16)
4. Literature Review (EUCLID 2019, 17-23)
5. Style Guide (EUCLID 2019, 24-26)
6. American vs. British English (EUCLID 2019, 27-35)
7. Chicago Style and Usage (EUCLID 2019, 44-55)

ACA-401/ACA-401D COURSEPACK PERIOD 1

1) INTRODUCTION

ACA-401D period one focused on writing academic essays, which involves constructing an initial plan, putting down our thoughts, ideas and expressions and the use of evidence to support the points raised. The book started with a detailed discussion on essay writing basics, planning, draft writing, drafts editing to completing the essay, referencing and submitting the final work (EUCLID 2019, 1). Period one coursework has nine chapters (1 to 9). The contents include – plagiarism, some rule of thumb for writing papers, literature review, style guide, American versus British English, CMS Crib Sheet and Latin abbreviations and expressions. The topics are valuable as they provided insights on common mistakes to avoid while writing academic essays.

2) ESSAY WRITING BASICS

Chapter one of the ACA-401 period one talks about the essay writing basics focusing on writing academic essays. Writing an academic essay is an essential part of coursework in higher institutions. This means the basics of composition writing from

start to finish. Although I have been writing essays as far back as I can remember, this part of the coursework threw more light and have expanded my knowledge on how to organize my ideas. As we put down our thoughts, we need to think creatively and critically to ascertain our arguments' importance (EUCLID 2019, 2). This chapter also emphasizes why it is necessary to start essay drafts on time.

Time management is something to consider and improve on in essay writing. I have learnt from this chapter that dividing my work into various stages (having an essay plan) and allocating a time frame will make it manageable. In order words starting the essay on time gives enough room to read the draft severally and corrections made, especially with grammar. Grammatical errors can give a sentence a different meaning, hence the need to read through multiple times. As you read through, you can reframe or refine your work. This promotes good logical flow when reading the paper. If all these are strictly adhered to by the students, they will be writing essays effectively.

3) PLAGIARISM

Chapter two discussed plagiarism and the importance of citing the sources of our information when we write. Plagiarism is the presentation of published materials and ideas of someone else as if they were our own (Aveyard 2014, 173). Giving credit to the author when we quote, use visuals or statistics is recommended in academic essay writing. This means carefully representing the ideas of the author in our own words. This chapter teaches how to avoid plagiarism, using in-text citation, listing the cited works, using quotations marks and paraphrasing a writeup to avoid committing an academic offence (EUCLID 2019, 5-13). The study material highlighted the examples of paraphrasing with their format. I found this very interesting as I have seen and learnt from the passage that sometimes you may still give the author credit and may not have paraphrased rightly. Now I understand when to cite and when not to, especially if the information is standard.

4) RULES OF THUMB FOR WRITING PAPERS

Chapter three gave suggestions on how to write papers clearly from start to finish. While writing, one has to have theories to discuss the subject matter. The writer should state the primary thesis and give a detailed overview of the idea. I have learnt from this section not to create suspicion when I am writing but to go straight and discuss my points. I use to write long sentences, but now I have read that I should avoid long paragraphs and sentences. I believe the constant practice will give me mastery of this technique. Previously my essays have too many quotations. This is because I want to avoid plagiarism. It is somehow surprising for me to read here that we should quote passages only when it plays a crucial role in the paper (EUCLID 2019, 15). I am considering booking an appointment for tutorials on this so that I improve on my essays.

5) LITERATURE REVIEW; AMERICAN VS BRITISH ENGLISH

A literature review is the comprehensive study and interpretation of literature that relates to a particular topic (Aveyard 2014, 2). Chapter four dealt with the review of literature which is where most bulk of the writing is. Writing a literature review requires a consistent writing style. The author should specify the type of English (American or British) used (EUCLID 2019, 27-35). I did not know these matters in writing essays. My thinking was that as long as the grammar is correct, you can use it. This coursework has helped me realize the importance of sticking to a particular writing style and being consistent with the chosen style throughout the essay.

6) STYLE GUIDE; CHICAGO STYLE AND USAGE

Chicago endnotes and footnotes usage was discussed in the paper. Being conversant with endnotes and footnotes is essential and will guide me when writing my assignments. Most of the topics addressed in period one were new to me. Although I am striving to master the contents with mixed feelings and fear, this is a good foundation that every student should pass through to improve their writing skills.

The study material is critical and useful and has improved my knowledge of preparing myself to have persuasive academic essay writing. I have also learnt a lot and have identified some areas I was not doing well. For instance, proofreading was not so important to me. I write and submit and never really take time to go through the work. All those little things I ignore, I have seen that it matters in academic essay writing.

This study material is good and highly recommended to anyone who wants to stand out in academic essay writing.

7) CONCLUSION

A good essay presents points or information by citing credible sources. Writing an academic paper involves mastery of essay writing basics, presenting the argument through closely related facts, and noting the sources of information. The writer should investigate divergent views and reasons extracted and discussed. Consistency with writing styles helps the flow of the writeup. All work cited should be referenced to avoid plagiarism, and the writer should use the recommended manual. This is the summary of what I grabbed from response paper one. I will keep practising them to perfect my essay writing skills

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2019. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. 2nd ed. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University.

Helen Aveyard. 2014. *Doing a Literature Review in Health and Social Care: a practical guide*. 3rd ed. Berkshire, England: Open University Press.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.